

Toulouse Safe Place For Science Application Bibliography

Bibliographic details follow to supplement the hyperlinked citations in the individual form submissions by the team consisting of Associate Professor Suniti Karunatillake, Professor Maheshi Dassanayake, and Postdoctoral Scientist Carlos Gary-Bicas. Sorted alphabetically by last name of the first author.

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